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Need For Speed: Fast Wind Farm Optimization

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Abstract. The Wind in my Backyard (WIMBY) project is developing a web interface to aid communities in siting wind energy projects. As part of this siting tool, users will be able to find realistic wind farm layouts for any proposed site in Europe, given certain constraints. When designing this tool, there arises a need for speed: realistic layouts must be designed in computational times that are appropriate for a web interface. In this study, we compare two optimization algorithms: a gradient-based algorithm, referred to as stochastic gradient descent (SGD), and a gradient-free method, referred to as smart-start. The trade-offs between the optimal energy yield and optimization computational time are characterized via a parameter sweep, considering a site in Denmark. This analysis considered farms with 10, 25, and 50 turbines. We find that smart-start yielded the best results for very short computational times, and that SGD yielded layouts with higher energy yields when considering larger computational times.

1. Introduction

Placing wind turbines to maximize energy yield or value is the core of wind farm design. Usually, turbine positions are optimized using engineering flow models to estimate the associated Annual Energy Production (AEP). In wind projects, local communities should be able to assess the potential impacts of developing such projects via a free and open interface. Thus, our group is developing an online tool for said purposes. Part of this tool will include a geospatial map of Europe where the user can define an area of interest and propose different wind farm capacities (or number of turbines), boundaries, and exclusion zones to obtain a wind farm layout. Hence, speed is important: users should not wait too long for an estimated wind farm while assuring the final design is plausibly realistic. As part of the design of this tool, we have identified a need to select an appropriate algorithm based on the number of wind turbines and user wait time requirements.

In practice, performing reasonably fast layout optimizations is favorable when designing wind farms, especially given the time frame and multiple iterations that some projects within the industry often have. Although a consensus on which wake models and optimization algorithms are best to use, there is a need to speed up the simulation process while still obtaining realistic results. In addition, wind farms are often constructed with complex boundaries and exclusion zones, amounting to non-convex boundaries [1, 2]. Several studies have tackled the problem of wind farm layout optimization with convex and non-convex boundaries using both gradient-free and gradient-based methods [3, 4, 5, 6, 1]. In addition, past research focused on the computational expense in optimizations with convex boundaries using boundary-grid

optimization [7]. Besides the need for modeling areas with exclusion zones when performing layout optimization, the representation of complex terrain in the simulation is equally important for land-based projects. Some studies have explored the implications of modeling complex terrain [1, 8, 9, 10], where some have focused on improving the wake modeling, and others tackled the problem with convex-shaped polygon boundary constraints. In terms of the optimization approach, gradient-based algorithms have often been reported to better explore the design space and find better solutions as the problem increases in size [11, 12, 13, 5].

The motivation for the present study comes from the development of a tool capable of producing optimal wind farm layouts from user-defined information. This tool is part of the Wind in My Backyard (WIMBY¹) project, which allows users to select an area within Europe to build a wind farm based on some basic parameters such as wind farm size (number of turbines), turbine size and capacity, terrain properties, among others. The WIMBY Wind Power Assessment Tool obtains its wind resource data from the New European Wind Atlas (NEWA) database [14, 15] and is capable of modeling non-convex boundaries through exclusion zone layers. One key factor in the development of the tool is the possibility for users to obtain optimized layouts in their area of choice for the minimum possible time.

In this study, we investigate and compare the trade-offs between computational time and AEP maximization for a given set of turbine locations within a specified area using the open-source TOPFARM [16] and PyWake [17] frameworks. These trade-offs will inform the design of our siting tool. We have chosen a site representative of a land-based area similar to those the tool would encounter, that is, with complex terrain and exclusion zones as boundary constraints. The modeling of irregular terrain is done the Jensen wake deficit model [18] by including wind speed ups in the calculation of the local wind speed. Our main goal is directed towards suggesting a set of parameters for the chosen algorithms depending on the available wait time described by the user. With this configuration, the best possible AEP can be obtained for the desired simulation time.

Section 2 describes the methods used in the study, including the optimization problem, flow modeling, as well as the algorithms chosen for the simulations. In Section 3, the setup of the site and optimization algorithms are introduced. The results and discussion are presented in Section 4, and lastly, the conclusions of the study are given in Section 5.

2. Methods

The objective function is the wind farm's AEP and the problem is constrained in terms of minimum turbine spacing and boundary constraints represented as inclusion or exclusion zones. The corresponding optimization problem is defined as

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \underset{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}}{\text{maximize}} && \text{AEP}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \\
 & \text{subject to} && \sqrt{(x_i - x_j)^2 + (y_i - y_j)^2} \geq S_{\min}, \quad \forall i, j \in I : i \neq j \\
 & && C_i \geq 0, \quad \forall i \in I \\
 & && x_l \leq x_i \leq x_u \\
 & && y_l \leq y_i \leq y_u
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where x and y are the turbine coordinate positions, x_l and y_l are the lower bounds for the horizontal and vertical wind farm boundaries, respectively, and x_u and y_u correspond to the upper bounds of the wind farm boundary. The minimum allowable inter-turbine spacing is defined as S_{\min} and measured in rotor diameters. For this study, we use $S_{\min} = 2$. C_i is the distance between turbine i and the nearest boundary, as defined in [2]. A positive C_i corresponds

¹ <https://www.wimby.eu/>

to a turbine inside of an inclusion zone, and for a negative C_i , the wind turbine is inside an exclusion zone.

We examine two open-source optimization algorithms: *smart-start* [19] and Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) [20]. The gradient of the turbine boundary constraint is computed via the methodology described in [2].

2.1. Flow Modeling in Complex Terrain

Since we are dealing with complex (i.e. non flat and non homogeneous) terrain, the probability distribution for the wind speed and wind direction in the site becomes non-uniform, meaning dependent on the wind turbine positions. One way to represent these irregularities is within the wake model itself [8]. However, in this study, the complex wind resource is modeled considering wind speedups due to the non-homogeneous terrain, which are included in the calculation of the local wind speed used in the wake model. These parameters are given from the NEWA input dataset. In this study the center point of the wind farm has been selected as the reference point for speedup calculation. The speedup is defined as:

$$S_{jxyh} = \frac{A_{jxyh} \cdot \Gamma(1 + 1/k_{jxyh})}{A_{jh}^{ref} \cdot \Gamma(1 + 1/k_{jh}^{ref})} \quad (2)$$

where the indices used are; x-coordinates (x), y-coordinates (y), height over ground (h), and wind direction (j). \mathbf{A} is the Weibull scale parameter, \mathbf{k} is the Weibull shape parameter, and Γ is the gamma function for the calculation of the Weibull distribution's mean.

We then represent the undisturbed local wind speed U_{ijt} as that one affected by the speedups (S) with indices corresponding to: free stream wind speed (i), turbine location (t) and wind direction (j). To obtain S_{jt} from S_{jxyh} a linear interpolation method is applied.

$$U_{ijt} = S_{jt}U_{i,\infty} \quad (3)$$

The AEP is then defined as

$$\text{AEP}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = 8760 \sum_{j=1}^{N_\theta} \sum_{u=1}^{N_u} \sum_{t=1}^{N_{wt}} P(U_{ijt} - \Delta u_{ijt}) \rho(U_{i,\infty}, \theta_{\infty j}) \quad (4)$$

where P is power from the power curve, $U_{ijt} - \Delta u_{ijt}$ is the undisturbed local wind speed that includes the velocity deficit (Δu) associated with wake effects, which depends on the turbines' coordinates, \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} , and ρ is the site probability mass function. The free stream wind direction is defined as $\theta_{j,\infty}$ and 8760 is the number of hours in a year.

To model the wake effects that arise from the interaction of the wind turbines, we use the PyWake Jensen wake deficit model [18, 17, 21], with the associated default parameter settings. This includes a Squared Sum superposition model. The velocity deficit is defined as:

$$\Delta u_{ijt} = U_{ijt} \sum_{k=1}^K 2a_k \left(\frac{r_k}{r_k + \alpha \Delta x_k} \right)^2 \quad (5)$$

where k sums across all K turbines upstream of turbine t , Δx_k is the downstream distance, α is the wake expansion parameter, and a_k is the induction factor associated with turbine k , computed based on [22]. The cross-stream distance between turbines k and i must be less than $r_k + \alpha \Delta x_k$ in order for turbine k to be considered upstream of turbine i . The induction factor is expressed through a third-order polynomial following a Blade Element Momentum implementation as:

$$a = k_3 C_T^3 + k_2 C_T^2 + k_1 C_T \quad (6)$$

where $k_1 = 0.2460$, $k_2 = 0.0586$ and $k_3 = 0.0883$.

We used the Vestas V80 wind turbine model, which has a rotor diameter of 80 m, a hub height of 70 m, and a rated power of 2 MW.

2.2. Smart Start Algorithm

The *smart-start* algorithm is a gradient-free method used to solve wind farm layout optimization problems. It can be used as a gradient-free option on its own or a gradient-based one when coupled with other optimization algorithms, such as Sequential Least Squares Programming (SLSQP), for example. The main objective of *smart-start* is to improve the initial guess of a wind farm's layout. It does so by placing turbines iterative and sequentially only in areas with the best wind resources.

A set number of points in a regular grid defines the domain, which the algorithm uses to define an array with all the possible discretized positions of the wind turbines. From these positions, the ones that violate the boundary constraint are removed, and the AEP is calculated considering the wake effects of already placed turbines. From the points with the highest AEP, the algorithm randomly selects a point i to place the next turbine. Then, the algorithm will remove i and evaluate the spacing constraints, discarding all points that violate these constraints. Wind turbines are thus placed sequentially as the process described above repeats until all available wind turbines are situated. One key aspect of the algorithm is that it ignores the wake effects (reduction in AEP) of the previously added turbine.

Since the choice of points is performed randomly, *smart-start* is built with a randomness percentage parameter ($random_{pct}$) which allows the user to define the desired degree of randomness when selecting a point i . For $random_{pct} = 0$, the algorithm will place the turbine at the best position, i.e. that with the highest AEP. On the other hand, $random_{pct} = 100$ will place the turbines entirely randomly, evaluating only the possible violation of spacing and boundary constraints. When the $random_{pct}$ falls in between 0 and 100, the number of points available with high AEP increases, and so the algorithm chooses one of those potential points randomly. As the size of the domain is represented by the grid resolution, this parameter becomes crucial when using the algorithm. A finer grid will lead to better results but translates to higher computational time, whereas a courser grid will most likely yield a lower value of AEP. However, memory issues arise when using *smart-start* with a very fine grid.

2.3. SGD Algorithm

The Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) algorithm is a gradient-based approach to solving wind farm optimization problems that aggregates the constraints as a single penalty term. Initially, the constraint gradients remain of similar magnitude to the AEP gradients. As the optimization progresses, the algorithm places more weight on the constraint gradients by increasing the constraint multiplier. A Monte Carlo simulation approach is taken to characterize the distribution of atmospheric conditions (wind speed and wind direction) used to calculate the AEP gradients. The wind farm power is defined as $P(x, y, U_{i,\infty}^{(k)}, \theta_{j,\infty}^{(k)})$, where k represents the number of samples chosen for each iteration.

In the algorithm, a set of free parameters can be manually defined to enhance the performance of a specific wind farm optimization problem. The degree of exploration is given by the initial and final learning rates, measured in units of distance. The initial learning rate is taken as the initial step size for the optimization, where a small value will result in little movement of the turbines at the start of the optimization, and a higher value will impact the penalty violations, increasing them disproportionately from the AEP gradients.

In addition, the number of iterations and number of samples k can also be defined by the user, which heavily impacts the optimization time. Setting up a large number of iterations gives more time for the algorithm to converge to the best result. Nonetheless, for problems of varying sizes, excessively high iteration counts may be unnecessary and could result in increased processing times, particularly in cases where the Annual Energy Production (AEP) has potentially reached convergence with fewer iterations. On the other hand, the number of samples will affect the computational time as the number of turbines in the farm increases. Lastly, the algorithm has an early stopping feature that allows it to speed up the optimization process by turning off AEP computations after a certain ratio of the initial learning rate has been reached.

3. Application

In this study, we used the *smart-start* and SGD algorithms to optimize wind farms of different sizes for a specific challenge site using the TOPFARM framework [16]. Our home institution, DTU Risø Campus, is used as the study site, where a detailed map with wind resource data and exclusion zones is constructed. The purpose of the study is to measure how the algorithms perform in terms of computational time for the three scenarios presented. To do this, we chose a series of parameters to carry out an exhaustive grid sweep and suggest potential configurations when using *smart-start* and SGD.

3.1. Site object

The wind resource data is given by the New European Wind Atlas (NEWA) database, more specifically, the NEWA microscale Geographic Information System (GIS) database [14, 15]. For the exclusion zones, the spatial data was pre-processed with GIS functions and encompasses a series of layers representing roads and marine and land-based protected areas. The effect of the terrain and land use on the wind is implicitly included in the input wind resource data.

The information of the NEWA microscale data is used to define an *XRSite* object in PyWake, with a non-uniform wind resource. Exclusion zone layers are used to define the non-convex exclusion/inclusion zones to use as boundary constraints. Figure 1 shows the site used for the optimization problem. The site is comprised of a dataset that represents the wind resource and terrain data with coordinates x , y , wind direction sectors, and heights. For the study, we interpolated the values of the dataset for the turbine's hub height (70 m). Each direction sector is associated with a probability mass function as well as the Weibull A and k parameters to define the sector's wind speed.

Figure 1 shows the site used for the optimization problem, which is located in Denmark around the Risø site, where DTU Wind is located. A buffer is applied to give the lines of the exclusion zones an area, where for roads a value of 50 meters was chosen and for marine and land-based protected areas a buffer of 10 meters was implemented.

3.2. Optimization

To estimate the desired configuration of the aforementioned algorithms for fast wind farm layout optimizations, we chose three wind farm sizes: 10, 25, and 50 turbines. The objective function is defined by the AEP, as in Equation 1, with the individual wind turbine positions as the design variables. The inclusion zones illustrated in Figure 1 represent the problem constraints, in addition to the inter-turbine spacing of 2 rotor diameters (160 m).

Automatic differentiation (AD) via the Python library autograd [23] was used to calculate the gradients of the AEP for the SGD algorithm. For the *smart-start* approach, the algorithm was used to calculate the best locations for the wind turbines, and the AEP was computed via the Jensen wake model without the addition of a solver to both speed up the simulation time and measure the robustness of the algorithm.

Figure 1: Site considered for the study. The wind resource is shown as a contour plot with the mean wind speed in the site. The exclusion zones where turbines are not to be placed are shown in light gray.

An HPC cluster [24] was used to run the optimizations, as it allows the use of batch jobs for parallelization. Several nodes were used for the simulations, each of them consisting of 2x16 processors AMD EPYC 7351 with a total of 32 cores and 128 GB of RAM. The time recorded represents the total time it takes for the solver to converge to the final solution after the problem with the design variables and constraints has been defined.

Table 1 and 2 show the parameters chosen for the grid sweep for both the *smart-start* and the SGD algorithms, respectively. For the wind speeds, a range between 3 and 25 m/s is selected, and for the wind direction, a range of 0–360° is chosen. With *smart-start*, the wind speed and wind direction are discretized when computing the AEP to find the optimal turbine positions. As SGD performs Monte Carlo sampling of the wind rose, the wind speed and direction discretizations were fixed at 1 m/s and 1°, respectively. The final AEP associated with both algorithms' solutions is reported using 1 m/s and 1° bins.

Table 1: Grid Sweep Parameters chosen for the Smart-Start algorithm.

Parameter	Values
Randomness percentage [%]	10, 30, 50, 70, 90, 100
Resolution [-]	50, 100, 200, 400
Wind speed bin size [m/s]	22, 11, 6, 2
Wind direction bin size [°]	72, 32, 16, 4, 2, 1

4. Results and discussion

We present here the comparison between the *smart-start* and SGD algorithms. The main goal is to characterize which algorithm can yield fast results without compromising the AEP value too much and suggest the corresponding parameters for the setup. The SGD algorithm generally respects the constraint violations when the early stopping parameter is greater than zero and moves turbines to a valid position, ignoring the objective after a certain number of iterations [20]. In the final results, we only show those simulations with violations less than 0.5 m.

Table 2: Grid Sweep Parameters chosen for the SGD algorithm. Note that the initial learning rate is given in units of rotor diameters.

Parameter	Values
Early stop [-]	0, 0.05, 0.2, 0.8, 0.9, 0.98, 0.99, 1
Initial learning rate [D]	0.05, 0.1, 0.2, 0.5, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5
Number of samples [-]	10, 50, 100, 200, 500
Number of iterations [-]	200, 500, 1000, 2000
Final learning rate [m]	0.01, 0.1, 1

Figure 2 shows the Pareto front associated with the gathered simulation results in terms of the capacity factor. When using *smart-start*, it is possible to obtain very fast solutions, between 1 and 4 seconds, for all of the three wind farm cases. However, it was found that a resolution of 400 x 400 points proved unfeasible, as memory problems arose. This is presented as a limitation of the algorithm itself, and that a grid size of 200 x 200 points was the maximum it could handle with the computational resources available. For simulation times spanning more than 1 minute, the SGD algorithm outperforms the *smart-start*, converging to higher values of AEP. The choice of the best algorithm will rely mostly on the user wait time requirement. Because of this, we have arbitrarily chosen 3 different simulation times to analyze more closely, as denoted in Figure 2 by the dotted vertical lines. The chosen times are 4 seconds, 30 seconds, and 4 minutes.

At the selected times, the parameters for each algorithm associated with the highest AEP are extracted and shown in Tables 3 and 4. The idea is to present individual parameters set up for each algorithm and study case (simulation time and number of turbines) depending on the available user wait time. The empty slots represent those that did not yield better results when compared to the other algorithm for the same configuration.

Table 3: Best performing parameters associated with the results shown in Figure 2 for the *smart-start* algorithm. The empty parameters represent AEP results lower than those found for the SGD algorithm for the same study case.

Time [min]	0.07			0.5			4		
No turbines [-]	10	25	50	10	25	50	10	25	50
Randomness percentage [%]	10	10	100	-	-	-	-	-	-
Resolution [-]	100	50	50	-	-	-	-	-	-
Wind speed bin size [m/s]	2	2	2	-	-	-	-	-	-
Wind direction bin size [°]	16	72	1	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 4: Best performing parameters associated with the results shown in Figure 2 for the SGD algorithm. The empty parameters represent AEP results lower than those found for the *smart-start* algorithm for the same study case.

Time [min]	0.07			0.5			4		
No turbines [-]	10	25	50	10	25	50	10	25	50
Early stop [-]	-	-	-	0.05	0.8	0.8	0.05	0.8	0.98
Initial learning rate [D]	-	-	-	4	5	3	5	1	1
Number of samples [-]	-	-	-	10	10	10	50	50	200
Number of iterations [-]	-	-	-	200	500	200	1000	2000	2000
Final learning rate [m]	-	-	-	1	0.1	1	0.1	0.1	0.01

Figure 2: Pareto fronts for SGD and *smart-start* (SMST) derived for the selected wind farm sizes. The pareto front compares the capacity factor from the energy yield with the computational time of the optimizations. The vertical black dotted lines represent the simulation times: 4 seconds, 30 seconds and 4 minutes.

As a general rule, we recommend using *smart-start* to obtain very fast optimizations, no matter the wind farm size. For longer simulation times, the SGD algorithm yielded higher AEP and thus higher capacity factors when compared to *smart-start*, although the difference between them was not significant. If the user wait time is not limited, the SGD algorithm will tend to find better solutions, especially for configurations with more than 1,000 iterations and a greater number of samples.

For the parameters chosen in Tables 3 and 4, additional simulations were done considering random seeds for both algorithms. The variability in the results is shown in Figure 3 for the capacity factors of the different setups of time and wind farm size. Overall, it was found that the capacity factor values are consistent for all cases studied and do not exhibit a large spread. However, in the case of the *smart-start* algorithm, outliers in the measured computational time were found for a specific seed, which performed slower than the rest. It can be seen that going from 4 seconds to 30 seconds contributes noticeably to obtaining better results (higher AEP), but for this case, increasing the time does not add much value, as the difference in capacity factor between 30 seconds and 4 minutes is not significant. These outliers could be handled by stopping and restarting the optimization algorithm with a new seed if a particular seed takes too long.

From the results, it can be observed that using *smart-start* is preferable for obtaining reasonable results for very low computational time. As shown in Table 3, the best-found *smart-start* grid resolution decreases as the number of turbines increase, when considering a fast optimization run of 4 seconds (0.07 minutes). A lower resolution helps the algorithm find solutions faster, but not necessarily the optimal ones. It may be possible to use the initial guess from *smart-start* as a starting point for a gradient-based optimization (e.g. with an SLSQP

Figure 3: Histogram of results associated with the parameters from Tables 3 and 4. The light blue histograms represent the *smart-start* algorithm and the green ones the SGD.

solver) to converge to better solutions. Although this approach may converge to higher capacity values from those found in Figure 2, it may also increase the computational time considerably, for which such fast optimizations (under 5 seconds) might not be possible. On the other hand, the SGD algorithm proved to be better than *smart-start* when the user wait time available is longer than 30 seconds. It was observed that going from 1 to 10 minutes of simulation, a noticeable increase in the AEP was found when using the SGD algorithm, as seen in Figure 2. The obtained results are in line with the trends reported in the literature [11, 12, 13] when discussing gradient-free and gradient-based optimization methods.

The site chosen for study is considered a challenge for the optimization algorithms as it presents a large number of boundary discontinuities in the form of exclusion zones. Even though the amount of exclusion zones increases the number of constraints to be evaluated, the algorithms performed quite well and were able to find similar solutions when maximizing the AEP.

5. Conclusions

We have presented an initial set of results to guide future efforts in designing the WIMBY siting tool. The results are representative of a wind farm layout optimization performed in our home institution, DTU Risø Campus, for a non-uniform wind resource and complex terrain. Three case studies were selected with different wind farm sizes in order to explore the scalability of the problem when applying two optimization algorithms: *smart-start* and SGD. All of the numerical computations were made using the open-source tools developed at DTU Wind, TOPFARM, and PyWake. We studied the computational time required for convergence to a solution with both algorithms.

We found that for very fast computational times, *smart-start* outperformed the SGD

algorithm. However, as the user wait time increases, the SGD algorithm yields better designs. When looking at the variability of results obtained from simulations with many random seeds, it was observed that the capacity factor gain from 30 seconds to 4 minutes is not significant. This means that for some cases, a simulation of 30 seconds or 1 minute could be sufficient to obtain acceptable results with the SGD algorithm. The parameters suggested are indicative of simulations that yielded the best solutions. In practice, the optimization algorithm parameters can be selected using a nearest neighbor or linear interpolation.

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